

A Study of Matter and Atomism in Indian Philosophy

**Indian Journal of Sciences
and Systems**

ISSN: 2277-1999
Volume 4 Issue 2
July, 2014

Author:

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma

Email: kksharma69@yahoo.com

Corresponding Address:

C-7, Bank Men Colony, Kankarbagh,
Patna-800020, Bihar (India).
Contact: 9504782781.

Access this article online

URL: hdawi.com/journals/ijss/2498

Abstract

This paper reviews the various branches of Indian Philosophy especially those orthodox, including the *Sankhya*, *Vaisesika*, *Nyay*, and *Mimansha*. The purpose of the study was to investigate the manner philosophical foundations of chemistry can be developed amidst those literatures. The study has been mainly based upon the literature reviews whereby the original texts in Sanskrit and their translation along with digest and commentaries of different scholars were conducted. All those various facts of the philosophy was then corroborated with the modern knowledge of science.

It has been a clear mention about the atoms being the basic building block of every corporeal object in this universe. Even the shape of the atom is said to be globular. One atom joining another atom to form a dyad, triad, and then on creating the entire universe due to the geometrical progressions. It is also mentioned that the atoms cannot be destroyed through any means. The whole process of evolution was sequenced as *Akash* or ether emerged first, followed respectively by the gas, fire, water and earth. This would start the new debate that earth separated from the sun as a gas or as a fireball. It may be also a case that the earth may have existed in gaseous form just like Jupiter, Saturn, and Neptune.

Key words: *Indian Philosophy; Study of Matter; Atomism.*

Introduction:

Methods of Indian Philosophy of cognition of knowledge were very systematic and perhaps using those techniques they pronounced theories which could be never set aside by modern scientists and their experiments. Even many American and Jewish scientists started gossiping that those ancient wisdom may have been provided by ancient aliens. How scientists could be able to say anything about aliens without any scientific basis of their existence. Science is not a work of fiction without any basis.

Nyay and *Mimansha* Schools of Indian Philosophy clearly provided a basis for modern scientists to get the methods of cognition. It is the time to move ahead from those Greek Philosophies and look towards Indian Philosophical literatures where all those methods are findings are clearly and systematically described. Some of those texts were even could be easily dated back to those Greek philosophers. It is also most likely that Indian and Greeks have remained in contact may have exchanged those knowledge.

The historical background of contemporary philosophy of science and the scientific revolution needed to be revisited. There has been a great problem of induction, falsification, scientific realism, under a determination, constructive realism, especially in the development of scientific theories and methods.

The basic issues in the philosophy of science, such as the demarcation problem, the debate among competing accounts of the scientific method, the problem of induction, and the debate about scientific realism still not resolved. It needed to develop abilities to communicate philosophical concepts clearly.

Full Text:

It's generally believed that Greek philosophers first propagated *Atomism Theory* however *atomism has been very minutely* described in *Sankhya* and *Vaisesika* schools of Indian Philosophy much earlier. In those days there was very little difference between philosophy and science as it rightly puts forward that "Science tries to sort out, whereas Philosophy sums up things" (S. Radhakrishnanan, 1929).

Modern scientists wrote about *atoms* without seeing it. *Atoms* described differently in Physics and Chemistry. In Chemistry, *atom* defined as the basic structure of an element that could not break by any chemical means. A typical *atom* consisted of a nucleus of *protons* and *neutrons* with *electrons* orbiting the nucleus. The *standard model* of physics talked about several subatomic particles such as *quarks*, including *up* and *down* quarks, *tau*, *neutrinos* and now that model completed with the discovery of the *Higgs Boson* in the *Large Hadron Collider (LHC)* experiments (Teubner, 2009).

Dalton in the year 1805 very first time propagated the atomic theory (Britanica, 2013). From *Dalton* to *Large Hadron Collider (LHC)* experiments different perspective put forward, however, most of them remained inconclusive, mutually contradictory, and short lived. Even *Large Hadron Collider (LHC)* experiments disclosing nothing conclusive about *Higgs Boson*.

Dalton considered matter made up of atoms which incapable of subdivisions. In 1896, *J.J. Thomson* discovered that protons were positively charged and electrons negatively charged (J. J. Thomson, 1986). However, the charged behavior of any matter or particle could not differentiate in terms of positive or negative because how and why we call one negative or other positive. A negative charge or a positive charge are not apposite in nature, they just termed appositely. *Rutherford* found that atoms had a nucleus that positively charged (Rutherford, 1909). The *Bohr's* atomic model, *Chadwick's* discovery of neutrons and the further determination of charge, mass of electrons and protons cemented those *atomic models*.

Several other discoveries of subatomic particles such as *mesons*, *positrons*, *neutrinos*, and *antiprotons* also substantiated the modern atomistic theory (Bohr, 1911). However, *Bohr's* atomic model was considered most quantitatively successful which graduated by *Bury* and *Summerfield*. *Bohr's* model ultimately superseded by the *Wave Mechanical Theory*. *Max Planck* and *Albert Einstein* also supported the *Wave Mechanical Theory* through their interpretations. Further *Pauli's* exclusion and *Heisenberg's* uncertainty principle described several assumptions.

However, it could say that all those atomic theory almost a continuation moreover, rejection of each other and there was not uniformity. Further the chemical bonding theory that how atoms or molecules established bonds with other atoms or molecules, Lattice energy, Electron affinity, Lewis theory, Electromagnetic qualities of energy and matter, Radioactivity principles also accepted and rejected.

As per theories, so far put forward by different scientists over the period, it could say that *atoms* combined with each other to form elements, molecules, compounds, mixtures, ores, ions, and all other corporeal objects. Different theories persisted in Chemistry and Physics about the manner *atoms* mutually combined and separated. The *Standard Model* of particle physics talked about electromagnetic, weak, and strong forces and put aside the theories of gravitational forces and dark energy. *Standard model* so far successful on various issues, however still not able to answer all the questions.

Chemical sciences describing the chemical reactions through chemical equations, equilibriums, and balancing appeared not logical because they were never so easy. The definitions of elements, compounds, and ions put forward by scientists could no way term logical. They could be mere assumptions and largely tentative.

The scientific theories came very later, almost at the start of the nineteenth century. In chemistry and physics, atomic theory is a scientific theory of the nature of matter that stated matter is composed of discrete units called atoms. *Dalton*, *Bohr*, *Rutherford*, and *Chadwick*, all complimented each other. In 1924, *Louis De Broglie* proposed that all moving particles, particularly subatomic particles such as electrons exhibit a degree of wave like behavior. *Erwin Schrodinger* advanced this idea and explored whether or not the movement of an electron in an atom could better explain as a wave rather than as a particle and concluded that an electron exhibited a wave function instead of as a point particle. This approach elegantly predicted many of the spectral phenomena that *Bohr's* model failed to explain. Although this concept was mathematically convenient, it was difficult to visualize, and faced opposition. *Max Born* proposed that electrons could have both wave and particle attributes.

Therefore, science continued suffering from certain degrees of deficiencies. The knowledge of science in describing things or sorting out appeared scattered, isolated, confusing, and ill convincing at large. The progress of science since nineteenth century onwards on the study of the matter has been confusing, not resolving, inconclusive, and contradictory.

Milk, Curd, Butter, Cheese, Cottage Cheese (Paner), and Ghee all, despite the common origin and ingredients appeared and behaved differently because of

specific *atomic arrangements*. We could not produce Milk, Curd, Butter, Cheese, Cottage Cheese (Paneer), and Ghee in laboratory despite knowing almost all the ingredients because we have still to know the specific *arrangement of atoms*.

Appropriation could be the objective and *misappropriation* either caused or formed a part of the process towards *appropriation*. Therefore, whole creation could simply term as an appropriate or misappropriate *arrangements of atoms*.

Atoms were everywhere in this creation. All atoms had the same mass and weight always. It was the sole material of creation. We could not see it. *Atoms* were globular in shape and could no further divide or subdivided. *Atoms* could combine to another atom having similar or opposite properties that provided the basic construction of creation. *Atoms* could combine, remain in contact, and separate. *Atoms* could not quantify in terms of quanta. An *atom* combined from another atom to form *dyad* or *triad* might refer as molecules. There was not a multiplication of numbers of *atoms*, however; one *atom* combining another *atom* caused *geometrical progression*. Particle and anti-particle concepts definitely had gender aspects. Every matter could exhibit gender like properties. Living and non-living matter differed in *atomic arrangements*. Every *atomic arrangement* has its own tenure. *Atoms* remained in two paradoxical states and behaved oppositely to each other yet they combined, annihilated, and gave birth to new arrangements without losing their existence. Every atom definitely had its gender aspects.

Atoms could exhibit similar or different qualities under different conditions. If an *atom* exhibiting similar qualities combined with each other that could term as *the symmetrical arrangement of atoms*, whereas *atoms* with different qualities, meeting each other could term as *asymmetrical arrangement of atoms*. *Symmetrical arrangement of atoms* could form a medium conducive for sustenance. When two similar atomic arrangements come into mutual contact, there could not be any chemical reaction. Only contact of symmetrical and asymmetrical *arrangement of atoms* could result in energy and forces. Both the *Symmetrical* and *asymmetrical arrangement of atoms* could form the basis of creation of basic materials such as air, fire, water, and earth. *Atoms* of air mutually combined to create a larger air while an atom of water combines to create larger water.

Atoms could never destroy and always maintained their presence. However, dyads, triads, or gross matter could destroy. The gap between *atoms* filled by *Ether* and not by *Space* or *air*. Therefore, *Ether* worked as cementing and bonding material, however, *ether* never participated in any *atomic arrangement*, although it could be a result of certain *atomic arrangements*.

Without being part of any *atomic arrangement*, *ether* could play significant role in the creation and formed the basis for any *arrangements* or *disarrangements*. Whole creation appeared in *molecular form* and never in *atomic form*. *Arrangements of atoms*, therefore a continuous process because *atoms* remained ever active.

It was not possible to measure or estimate the qualities of *atoms*, however, matter made of atoms could have seventeen qualities such as *color, taste, smell, touch, number, size, individuality, conjunction, disjunction, priority, posteriority, knowledge, pleasure, pain, desire, aversion, and effort* (Sharma, 1960). When quality ceases to exist, it called activity. There were five activities such as *upward, downward, contraction, expansion, and movement* in general. *Ether, Time, Space, and Soul* were devoid of action because they incorporeal. When a quality resided in many objects called *generality* while resided in one object called *particularity*. Absolute non-existent was eternal.

Atoms considered as the root cause of the world of objects. *Atoms* could define as uncaused, un-manifested, unintelligent, and ever active yet all worlds and its objects contained in its bosom. *Atoms* remained always active due to inbuilt consciousness and cessation of activity would only occur when *atoms* lose its consciousness.

Qualities of matter acquired and exhibited only after *atomic arrangement* and in molecular form. A matter formed after appropriate or misappropriate arrangement of atoms exhibited several properties including magnetic and electromagnetic. Forces, including gravity resulted due to *arrangement of atoms*, however, gravitational forces could not be the universal force of the creation and in fact, it worked within limited geographical boundaries.

The matter could convert into different states such as solid, liquid, and gas due to specific *atomic arrangements*. The properties of *matter* could acquire and cease to exist. *Atoms* usually had two states such as *intelligent* and *unintelligent*. *Living* and *non-living* matter all resulted due to the specific arrangement of *atoms*. Any *matter* usually underwent three stages such as *equilibrium, loss of equilibrium, and coming back to equilibrium*. Matter exhibited different effects and properties during all those three stages.

Equilibrium, literary meant real or existent and considered responsible for the manifestation of objects in consciousness. It referred as goodness and produced pleasure. It's regarded as light and bright, buoyant, and illuminating. It also further said that the luminosity of light, power of reflections, upward movements, pleasure, happiness, contentment, and bliss all due to it. Its color described as white.

Loss or departure from equilibrium could literary meant foulness termed as the principle of motion. It

produced pain, restless activity, feverish efforts, and wild stimulation. It usually remained mobile and its color as red.

Coming back to equilibrium, literary meant darkness and could term as *a principle of inertia*. It produced apathy and indifference. Ignorance, sloth, confusion, bewilderment, passivity, and negativity could be its consequences. It termed heavy and enveloping and such oppressed to *equilibrium*. It also opposed to *losing equilibrium* as it could arrest activity. Its color said as dark.

Those properties exhibited by the mother during those three stages never separated. They could conflict and yet cooperate with one another and always found intermingled. If all those properties held in *equilibrium*, *nothing* happened. The predominance of one property over other disturbed the equilibrium.

There were forces produced due to conjunction and disjunction of *atomic arrangements*. The forces caused motion and vice versa. The effects of forces could be light, sound, and motion and vice versa. Forces also produced due to, and cause orbital and axial movements of matter. All motions and effects short lived and appear during the period of transition. Those axial and orbital movements performed in coordination held the objects of those planets together in their respective position in the space.

The energy stored in matter. Free energy automatically and instantly converts into matter due to *atomic arrangements*. *Atoms* everywhere in this universe. Energy and forces could induce *atomic arrangements*. The energy required a medium to travel. Energy could not produce, exist, and propagate on its own and required a medium. Energy utilized instantly it produced. Therefore, it required continuous generation and usage of electricity we could not store electricity like water, gas or other matter. Energy could turn into mass and mass could burst into energy. Energy could be the output of the

References:

- Bohr, N. (1911). *Bohr's Atomic Theory*. Denmark.
 Britanica, E. (2013). *John Dalton's Atomic Theory*. Retrieved from <http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/150287/John-Dalton/217770/Atomic-theory>
 J. J. Thomson. (1986). *Charged Behavior of Sub Atomic Particles*. London: Oxford.
 Rutherford. (1909). *Auther Atomic Model*. London.
 S. Radhakrishnanan, D. (1929). *Indian Philosophy*. London: Oxford.
 Sharma, C. (1960). *A Critical Survey of Indian Philosophy*. New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidas.
 Teubner, D. T. (2009). *The Standard Model*. Retrieved from THE STANDARD MODEL. By Dr T Teubner. University of Liverpool. Lecture presented at the School for Experimental High Energy Physics Students: www.stfc.ac.uk/ppd/resources/pdf/standardmodel09.

incompleteness of state of *atomic arrangements*. Light could be the universal effect and exhibited different properties in the different arrangement of atoms or mediums.

We grew hearing that apiece separated from the sun and consecutively get cold due to rain and became the earth. In fact, on this basis of my theory of *atomic arrangements* I would say that there was no difference between sun and earth as they both could part of the same process of *atomic arrangements*. Sun still burring whereas earth still burring beneath the surface, however certain part turned into water and other matter. Life started first in water due to the specific arrangements of *atoms* that sustained due to plantations. Life started on land after water.

If we apply those theories of *atomic arrangements* described it could say that the sun could turn into water that further could produce earth like matter. Even *Jupiter* and *Saturn* could turn into a fireball in the process to produce water and earth like matter. There could be systematic sequencing of evolution, such as air or gas turning into fire, water produced due to fire and the remaining matter appeared as earth like materials. Sun and Earth both could have remained in gaseous form earlier like *Jupiter* and *Saturn*.

Figure 1: Globular shape of Atom & Geometrical Progression of Atomic Arrangements

